

16 667 or 15 625 cm^{-1} which can often be resolved into at least three components, which agree with square-planar structure of copper(II) complexes.

The magnetic moment values of the nickel(II) azomethyne Schiff base complexes and their pyridine adducts are in the range 2.91–3.15 B.M. These complexes are green and their spectra are similar and characteristic of six-coordinate nickel(II), displaying the ν_1 , ν_2 and ν_3 transitions defined by the bands at 10 640–11 500, 16 666–18 500 and 22 900–25 000 cm^{-1} , respectively. The observed ν_2/ν_1 ratio values (1.56–1.60) fall well in the range of an octahedral structure.

In the ir spectra, no broad band appears near 2 700 cm^{-1} indicating that H-bonded OH hydrogen of both the β -diketones get dissociated after complexation. The two medium bands at 3 040 and 2 860–2 980 cm^{-1} correspond to C–H stretching of phenyl and methyl group respectively. All the mixed azomethyne and their pyridine adduct complexes show a band at 1 590–1 600 cm^{-1} (C=N) which confirms that both the β -diketone molecules condensed with ammonia in presence of metal ion and form amine Schiff base complexes. In all the mixed β -diketonamine Schiff base complexes, the strong band at 1 560 cm^{-1} can be attributed to the resonance between C–O–M and C=N...M links. In all these compounds a second band appears near 1 505 cm^{-1} , which can be attributed to the C=C link, same as reported by Bellamy and Branch⁵. The complexes of cobalt(II) and nickel(II) show a broad band at 3 600–3 400 cm^{-1} indicating the presence of coordinated water molecules⁶. The octahedral geometry of the complexes accounts for the association of two water molecules with the metal ion. While in pyridine adducts, this band disappeared. There is also a medium band at 3 320 cm^{-1} corresponding to NH stretching frequency. In many compounds this band is very weak due to a broad band that appears upto 3 300 cm^{-1} . Therefore, it is very difficult to distinguish OH and NH absorption bands.

In order to determine the thermal stability and the number of water molecules associated with the mixed amine Schiff base metal chelates the thermogravimetric analysis was carried out. DTG-thermogram for the copper(II) chelates reveals no weight-loss upto 200° indicating that there is no water of crystallisation or coordinated water present in the compounds. The nickel(II) chelates lost 6.5–8.5% of their weight at 50–200°, which corresponds to two water molecules. The weight-loss appearing after 120° indicates the presence of coordinated water in the complex. In the cobalt(II) chelates there is a weight-loss of about 3.0–3.5% below 100°, indicating the presence of water of crystallisation (absorbed water). The weight-loss of 7.0–8.0% upto 170° in the mixed imine cobalt(II) chelates indicates the presence of coordinated water molecules. While the thermogram of the pyridine adducts of the cobalt(II) and nickel(II) complexes show no loss upto 150°. The thermal stability order: $\text{Ni}^{II} > \text{Cu}^{II}$

was derived from the decomposition temperature obtained from DTG curves.

References

1. P. FRIEYER, E. BUCHHOLTZ and O. BAUER, *J. Pract. Chem.*, 1931, **129**, 163; F. BONATI and R. UGO, *J. Organometal. Chem.*, 1967, **7**, 167.
2. B. T. THAKER and P. K. BHATTACHARYA, *J. Inorg. Nucl. Chem.*, 1975, **37**, 615; *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 1976, **14**, 619; 1979, **17**, 371.
3. U. DORASWAMI and P. K. BHATTACHARYA, *J. Inorg. Nucl. Chem.*, 1975, **37**, 1665.
4. A. B. P. LEVER, "Inorganic Electronic Spectroscopy", Elsevier, Amsterdam, 1968, p. 249.
5. BELLAMY and BRANCH, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1954, 655
6. J. S. DWIVEDI and U. AGRAWAL, *J. Inorg Nucl Chem.*, 1973, **35**, 2229

Chromium(III) and Iron(III) Complexes of Isonitrosoketone Thiosemicarbazones

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THE metal complexes derived from thiosemicarbazones of diacetyl monoxime¹ and α -oximinobenzoylacetonilide² constitute an important class of antineoplastic agents endowed with interesting spectral features. Therefore, we ventured to synthesise the metal complexes of the related ligands, i.e. isonitrosoacetophenone thiosemicarbazone and its 4-chloroderivative and to characterise them with the aid of chemical and physicochemical methods of analysis.

Experimental

Isonitroso/4-chloroisonitrosoacetophenone was prepared³ and then condensed with thiosemicarbazide⁴ to obtain pure samples of the ligands.

A mixture of hot ethanolic solutions of $\text{CrCl}_3 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (25 cm^3 , 0.01 mol) and the ligand (25 cm^3 , 0.02 mol) was refluxed on a water-bath for about 4 h. On cooling and simultaneous trituration with petroleum ether (b.p. 60–80°) it yielded a brown amorphous solid, which was washed with ethanol-petroleum ether mixture (1 : 1, v/v) and dried over P_2O_5 under reduced pressure, (70%).

CrCl_3 was converted to $\text{Cr}(\text{SCN})_3/\text{Cr}(\text{CN})_3$ by metathesis and the latter was used to synthesise the thiocyanate/cyanide complexes.

Iron(III) complexes were prepared by adopting the same procedure as described above using FeCl_3

(anhydrous). The complexes were analysed for metal, S, Cl and N employing standard methods.

Conductivity measurements were carried out on an Elico conductivity bridge for complexes in DMF ($10^{-3}M$ solution). Magnetic susceptibility measurements were made at 27° using Gouy method. Ir spectra were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer 983 spectrophotometer, far-ir on a polytech FIR-30 spectrophotometer using KBr pellet, uv-visible-near ir spectra (300–1250 nm) of the complexes (in DMF) on a Carl-Zeiss 5U-2P spectrophotometer in 1 cm quartz cells, and Mössbauer spectra of the Fe^{III} complexes on a constant acceleration spectrophotometer coupled with a scalar analyser at 300 K using 5 meV ^{57}Co in Rh matrix as source.

Results and Discussion

Data on physical properties and chemical analysis are furnished in Table 1. The observed conductance values agree well with those reported for 1 : 1 electrolytes.

From ir spectral data, it is observed that both intra- and inter-molecular hydrogen bonding exist

in ligands as noted from the negative shift of the order of 250 cm^{-1} for ν_{OH} ($\sim 3400\text{ cm}^{-1}$) and a slight negative shift coupled with reduction in intensity for ν_{NH} ($\sim 3300\text{ cm}^{-1}$). The spectra of the ligand in acetonitrile solution are compared with those of the complexes in solid state.

The bonding taking place through N(azomethine), N(oximino) and S(thiocarbonyl) to the central metal ion can be proved from the shift in band frequencies of the following groups as suggested by various authors⁵. The ν_{CN} band ($\sim 1600\text{ cm}^{-1}$) shows a positive shift ($3-83\text{ cm}^{-1}$) in all the complexes so also the $\nu_{N=N}$ band ($\sim 900\text{ cm}^{-1}$) which shows positive shift of the order of $5-45\text{ cm}^{-1}$. Both these effects indicate bonding through azomethine N. ν_{NO} ($\sim 1020\text{ cm}^{-1}$) band suffers positive shift ($5-15\text{ cm}^{-1}$) on complexation indicating ligation through oximino N. $\nu_{CS} + \nu_{CN}$ ($\sim 760\text{ cm}^{-1}$) as well as ν_{CS} ($\sim 690\text{ cm}^{-1}$) vibrations undergoing negative shift ($2-50\text{ cm}^{-1}$) with reduction in intensity in a few cases, speak of 'S' (C=S) coordination. In addition, far-infrared spectra of the complexes show medium strong bands at ~ 300 and $\sim 450\text{ cm}^{-1}$ which are assigned to ν_{M-S} and ν_{M-N} vibrations respectively.

TABLE 1—ANALYTICAL AND PHYSICAL DATA OF COMPLEXES

Sl. no.	Compd.	Colour	M.p. °C	Analysis % : Found/(Calcd.)				Ω^{-1}	$\lambda_M\text{ cm}^3\text{ mol}^{-1}$
				M	N	Cl	S		
1.	$Cr(INAPT-H)_2Cl$	Brown	147d	9.73 (9.81)	20.97 (21.14)	6.56 (6.69)	12.01 (12.10)	85.11	
2.	$Cr(Cl.INAPT-H)_2C$	Brown	149	8.57 (8.68)	18.67 (18.71)	17.65 (17.76)	10.63 (10.71)	68.18	
3.	$Cr(INAPT-H)_2CN$	Brown	163d	9.83 (9.99)	24.12 (24.22)	—	12.25 (12.32)	69.95	
4.	$Cr(Cl.INAPT-H)_2CN$	Brown	162d	8.69 (8.82)	21.31 (21.39)	11.91 (12.03)	10.79 (10.88)	81.22	
5.	$Cr(INAPT-H)_2SCN$	Brown	125d	9.33 (9.41)	22.64 (22.81)	—	17.32 (17.41)	75.48	
6.	$Cr(Cl.INAPT-H)_2SCN$	Brown	151d	8.28 (8.37)	20.29 (20.28)	11.24 (11.41)	15.39 (15.48)	70.35	
7.	$Fe(INAPT-H)_2Cl$	Reddish brown	183	10.32 (10.46)	20.72 (20.99)	6.48 (6.64)	11.85 (12.01)	77.85	
8.	$Fe(Cl.INAPT-H)_2Cl$	Reddish brown	101d	9.23 (9.27)	18.51 (18.59)	17.52 (17.65)	10.57 (10.64)	74.42	
9.	$Fe(INAPT-H)_2CN$	Reddish brown	127d	10.47 (10.65)	23.91 (24.04)	—	12.18 (12.23)	71.31	
10.	$Fe(Cl.INAPT-H)_2CN$	Reddish brown	109	9.38 (9.41)	21.17 (21.25)	11.84 (11.95)	10.71 (10.81)	71.95	
11.	$Fe(INAPT-H)_2SCN$	Reddish brown	139d	9.91 (10.03)	22.51 (22.66)	—	17.09 (17.28)	89.01	
12.	$Fe(Cl.INAPT-H)_2SCN$	Reddish brown	116d	8.87 (8.93)	20.09 (20.16)	11.21 (11.34)	15.30 (15.38)	80.81	

TABLE 2—ELECTRONIC SPECTRAL AND MAGNETIC SUSCEPTIBILITY DATA OF Cr^{III} COMPLEXES

Complex no.*	ν_1 kK	ν_2 kK	ν_3 kK	Dq kK	B' cm^{-1}	β	Z	λ' cm^{-1}	γ	L.F.S.E. kcal mol^{-1}	μ_{eff} B.M.
1.	14.92	22.02	34.23	1.492	765.4	0.834	2.08	86.50	0.972	51.17	3.58
2.	14.92	22.27	33.24	1.492	649.5	0.708	1.48	72.50	0.768	51.17	3.58
3.	14.97	21.27	33.39	1.497	657.9	0.717	1.52	73.50	0.816	51.32	3.70
4.	14.70	21.27	33.13	1.470	686.1	0.747	1.67	76.90	0.854	50.42	3.41
5.	15.38	22.22	34.62	1.538	713.0	0.777	1.73	80.4	0.893	52.75	3.73
6.	15.15	21.73	33.91	1.515	679.6	0.740	1.63	76.10	0.845	51.95	3.55

*Sl. no. as in Table 1.

The slight deviation of μ_{eff} values (0.15–0.42 B.M.) of the Cr^{III} complexes at 300 K from spin-only value (3.88 B.M.) of octahedral type high-spin Cr^{III} may be due to tetragonal distortion⁶. The μ_{eff} values of the Fe^{III} complexes lie in the range 4.42–4.92 B.M. which are lower than those of a high-spin d^5 ($S=5/2$) configuration (5.83 B.M.) and much higher than those of low-spin ($S=1/2$) configuration (1.73 B.M.).

The three expected spin allowed $d-d$ transitions for an octahedral Cr^{III} ion with ${}^4A_{2g}$ ground state are ${}^4T_{2g} \leftarrow {}^4A_{2g}(\nu_1)$, ${}^4T_{1g}(F) \leftarrow {}^4A_{2g}(\nu_2)$ and ${}^4T_{1g}(P) \leftarrow {}^4A_{2g}(\nu_3)$ with increasing order of energies. Racah and other spectral parameters have been computed in accordance with the procedure adopted by Preti and Tosi⁷. The values of nephelauxetic parameter β (0.70–0.83) and effective nuclear charge Z (1.48–2.08) (Table 2) agree well with those observed in other Cr^{III} complexes derived from N and S donor ligands⁸. The metal-ligand covalency parameter (γ) which is analogous to nephelauxetic parameter is in the range 0.77–0.92 indicating the covalent nature of the complexes. The spin-orbit coupling constant has been calculated from Cole and Garrett's empirical relation: $\lambda = 0.0116(\beta + 1.080)^3 + 0.0062$, which imparts covalent character to metal-ligand bond. The octahedral Fe^{III} complexes exhibit low intensity broad bands in the region 15 380–18 860 cm^{-1} which are due to $d-d$ transitions.

The experimentally measured Mössbauer parameters such as isomer shift (IS) and quadrupole splitting (QS) reveal the geometry of the complexes. The IS values (0.27–0.31 mm s^{-1}) are considerably lower than those observed in typical high-spin octahedral Fe^{III} complexes⁹ (0.4–0.9 mm s^{-1}) but much higher than those of Fe^{III} in the low-spin state (0.04–0.09 mm s^{-1}). Thus the present complexes are regarded as high-spin type possessing spin cross-over properties similar to those reported by other investigators¹⁰ for Fe^{III} complexes. The QS values (0.62–1.04 mm s^{-1}) further suggest distorted Oh symmetry as assumed from electronic spectral data.

Thus the following structure has been tentatively proposed for the $\text{Fe}^{\text{III}}/\text{Cr}^{\text{III}}$ complexes.

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References

1. R. RAINA and T. S. SRIVASTAVA, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 1982, **21**, 490.
2. D. M. PATEL, M. M. PATEL and M. R. PATEL, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 1985, **24**, 875.
3. F. J. WELCHER, "Organic Analytical Reagents", D. Van Nostrand, New York, 1955, Vol 3, p. 279.
4. N. SALDABOLS, A. CIMANIS, S. HILLERS, J. POPELIS, L. N. ALEKSEVA, A. ZILE and A. K. VALYNSKAYA, *Khim. Farm. Zh.*, 1974, **8**, 12.
5. M. J. M. CAMPBELL and R. GROZESKOWIAK, *J. Chem. Soc. (A)*, 1967, 396.
6. M. C. JAIN, R. K. SHARMA and P. C. JAIN, *J. Inorg. Nucl. Chem.*, 1984, **42**, 1229.
7. C. PRETI and G. TOSI, *Can J. Chem.*, 1974, **52**, 2845.
8. M. H. SONAR and A. S. R. MURTY, *J. Inorg. Nucl. Chem.*, 1977, **39**, 2155.
9. N. N. GREENWOOD and T. C. GIBB, "Mössbauer Spectroscopy", Chapman and Hall, London, 1971.
10. E. FRANK and G. R. EBELDO, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1966, **5**, 1453.

Studies on Metal Complexes of Thiosemicarbazone and *N*-Phenylthiosemicarbazone derived from 3-Acetylcoumarin

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THIOSEMICARBAZONES and semicarbazones possess a wide spectrum of medicinal properties¹. The biological activity of these compounds has often been related to their chelating ability with metal ions². In continuation of our studies on the metal complexes of thiosemicarbazones and semicarbazones, we report here the synthesis and characterisation of the Fe^{III} , Co^{II} , Ni^{II} , Cu^{I} , Zn^{II} , Pd^{II} , Cd^{II} and Hg^{II} complexes with 3-acetylcoumarin thiosemicarbazone (ACTS) and 3-acetylcoumarin *N*-phenylthiosemicarbazone (ACPTS).

Experimental

All the solvents and the other chemicals used were of AnalaR grade.

Preparation of ligands: 3-Acetylcoumarin was synthesised as reported earlier³. ACTS and ACPTS were prepared by refluxing for 3 h equimolar quantities of 3-acetylcoumarin and the appropriate thio-